

THE ANTECEDENTS AFFECTING SUSTAINABLE TOURISM MANAGEMENT IN THE EAST COAST TOURISM DEVELOPMENT ZONE

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Abstract

Sustainable tourism management can generate income and enhance related business that contribute to economic growth at both local and national level, promote natural and environmental conservation and local culture, create careers and income for local people as well as building long-term strength of local communities and the nation. This research study aims to 1) examine the level of the following variables; tourist attraction potential, leadership, government policy, innovation and sustainable tourism management, 2) explore the relationship among those variables; tourist attraction potential, government policy, leadership and innovation affecting the sustainable tourism management in the east coast tourism development zone, and 3) develop the model of sustainable tourism management in the east coast tourism development zone. The mixed research methodology was applied between quantitative and qualitative terms. In view of the quantitative term, the sample group consisted of 360 tourism operators in the east coast tourism development zone whereas its sample size was calculated based on the 20-time criteria of the observed variables and systematic sampling. Data collection was undertaken through questionnaires that were later analyzed by the structural equation modelling. For the qualitative term, an in-depth interview was conducted with 20 primary informants who were tourism management expertise in the east coast tourism development zone. The research findings revealed that the variables; tourist attraction potential, leadership, government policy, innovation and sustainable tourism management in the east coast tourism development zone were all at a high level, 2) the variables ; tourist attraction potential, leadership, government policy and innovation affected the sustainable tourism management in the east coast tourism development zone with statistical significance level of .05, and 3) the sustainable tourism management model as developed by the researcher was called GLTI-STM Model (G = Government Policy, L = Leadership, T = Tourist Attractions Potential, I = Innovation, STM = Sustainable Tourism Management). Additionally, the qualitative findings indicated that to manage the sustainable tourism in the east coast tourism development zone, the application of new technology and approaches such as 3D (Data Digitizing, Data Sharing, Digitalized Process), intelligence data base management system for tourism data, ecosystem strategy, creation of virtual tour experience and tourism applications are recommended for development and improvement of tourism patterns according to the sustainable tourism principle. The findings in this study can be also applied as a guideline to determine the policy for conservation of natural resources in parallel with the sustainable tourist attraction development, and to standardize the tourism management to be more effective at the international level for future creation of economic value.

Keywords: Sustainable Management, Government Policy, Leadership} Tourist Attraction Potential, East Coast Tourism

1. INTRODUCTION

Thailand's tourism industry plays a very important role in the development and stabilizes the country's economy by causing investment and building a business in many related supply chains such as the construction industry, product manufacturing industry, real estate development, transportation industry and other services, etc. The tourism is an important factor that causes employment spreading to local community. It creates economic growth and generates income for the people of the country. Even in a state of global economic slowdown which inevitably affects the Thai economy, the tourism business is still an important part that helps support the Thai economy. The incomes from Thai and foreign tourism in the first half of 2019 plays an important role, up to 17% of GDP, which is the same level as the previous year (Surawattananont, 2019).

Consistently, the tourism industry and other sectors that are constantly connected in the chain of tourism activities such as recreational business, travel business, food and beverage business, merchandise and souvenir business, hotel business, and transportation business, etc. creates Gross National Product (GDP) (Office of the Permanent Secretary for Tourism and Sports, 2021). In 2019, GDP of tourism values 3,005,552 million baht, representing 17.79 percent of the GDP. In addition, Thailand has realized the importance of tourism as a significant tool to drive the economy with the National Tourism Policy Act to promote and increase potential in tourism management and development directly and indirectly which promotes sustainable tourism management. The tourism development zone, moreover, is determined in line with the potential of tourist attractions in the country's regional areas. The eastern seaboard tourism development zone is one of the important tourism development zones of the country. It has been established under the National Tourism Policy Act because it is important world-known tourist attractions, including sandy beaches, seashores, islands, colorful festivals and events that are popular with both domestic and international tourists. This is to allow related agencies to integrate the policy into practice to achieve the goal (Office of the Permanent Secretary for Tourism and Sports, 2021).

Tourism in the eastern seaboard tourism development zone is a source of income. It is important and has many benefits to the economy and continues to grow. However, the single development of tourist attractions to gain popularity in order to generate economic income regardless the consequences that will occur in all aspects, both in the short term and in the long term, including the lack of powerful management may have a negative impact on the way of life of the community. The deterioration of resources and environment conflicts arises from unfair distribution of interests to the locality and other problems. In addition, the previous tourism situation also faced competition and high volatility, especially after the outbreak of COVID-19, the tourism industry faces even more challenges as the number of foreign tourists' travels down (Bhuiyan et al., 2020). It results in the tourism business in the eastern tourism development zone, which by taking advantage of the location and abundance of existing resources and referring to the behavior of tourists in the past, may not be as effective as before. The factors of the development of communication technology and internet networks, in addition, enable tourists to access information about tourist attractions as well as being

convenient in planning and making a reservation so that they can travel from anywhere and anytime. As a result, tourism entrepreneurs must learn and adapt to keep up the needs of tourists that are constantly changing.

Sustainable tourism is an important tourism management that has been widely discussed and accepted globally to be used as a guideline for tourism management and development, as in line with the National Tourism Policy Act that encourages sustainable tourism management. The tourism businesses must accommodate changes that can happen and change from the traditional tourism management to sustainable competitiveness after the COVID-19 epidemic (Higgins-Desbiolles, 2020; Palacios-Florencio et al., 2021). Tourist attractions must be developed by getting support from government agencies, private sectors, and local community and organization. Entrepreneurs in tourist attractions, furthermore, must have vision and can predict both positive and negative impacts on tourism as well as being able to apply technology and seek innovation to be used in tourism development to meet the needs of tourists. This is a way to develop sustainable tourism in the future (Ertac & Cankan, 2021).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Impact of Leadership on Sustainable tourism management

Leadership leads to customer loyalty and organizational performance. According to a literature review, Khalifa (2020), which studied factors affecting the competitiveness of tourism organizations for the Egyptian tourism industry to study the significant impact of strategic leadership on strategic planning efficiency, sustainable tourism practices and the competitiveness of tourist attractions as destinations, found that strategic planning efficiency has a significant impact on sustainable tourism practices and sustainable tourism practices have a significant impact on the competitiveness of tourist attractions as destinations. In addition, sustainable tourism practices mediate a positive influence of strategic leadership on competitiveness of tourist attractions as destinations. This study was a quantitative research by developing a questionnaire to survey tourism experts who are hotel managers and department heads of the hotel association of Egypt in Cairo and Sharm El-Shikh. A questionnaire of 510 sets was distributed and 355 valid questionnaires were received. Hypotheses were analyzed by structural equation modeling (SEM). The study results supported the hypothesis that sustainable tourism practices mediate a positive influence of strategic leadership on competitiveness of tourist attractions as destinations.

El-Aidie, Alseiri and Khalifa (2021) have studied sustainability and capacity in the competition of tourism in the United Arab Emirates using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire as a tool to collect data about respondents' opinions on a scaled basis (1= strongly disagree and 5= strongly agree). The sample was 355 tourism institutes in Abu Dhabi, The United Arab Emirates (UAE). The results have shown that leadership can play a key role in making individuals and institutions can create, utilize and apply knowledge to build core competencies needed to improve organizational learning. Moreover, strategic leadership plays an active role in developing organizations and organizational structures through the dissemination of organizational learning, dissemination of corporate culture and the stimulation of modern

technology. There is also a direct relationship between strategic leadership and corporate culture. Strategic leadership style that strategic leaders use to manage employees reflects the corporate culture which demonstrates the importance of strategic leadership, the effectiveness of the strategic plan and sustainable practices to improve and enhance the competitiveness of tourist attractions. The study indicates that strategic leadership plays an important role in facilitating and promoting effective implementation of strategic plans and sustainable practices that will reflecting on the joint performance of tourism organizations in the UAE (Khalifa, 2020).

2.2 Impact of Innovation on Sustainable tourism management

From the literature review on the elements of innovation, it was found that innovation leads to the creation of measures as follows: 1) product innovation, i.e. activities that support initiative ideas, ability to continuously create new products, new product or service presentation, improvements in key technical specifications, components and software materials of products and services, and technology pursuit consistent with new product development, 2) service innovation, i.e. giving opportunities to participate in brainstorming to seek new approaches in changing the traditional practice, adoption of new production methods or improved delivery, use of efficient information technology and communication systems of the agency enabling the operation to achieve its goals with quality, changing the important technique of a device or software, and seeking technology consistent with new process development, 3) marketing innovation, i.e. the target market for tourists in line with the services, product placement, product promotion or pricing, new marketing developments related to product design or packaging, image improvement which is a change in product perception and services in line with the target group of service users, using technology to develop marketing, and 4) organizational innovation, i.e. using technology to improve process by reducing duplicated functions, promoting new generation personnel with knowledge and interest in innovative technology to play a role in changing the work culture with a customer-centered approach towards quality service, focusing on creativity that meets the needs of tourists in terms of safety, health, transportation and medical treatment, creative concept improvement in the workplace, generating a paradigm for creating innovative capabilities to bring new ways of organization to use in business (Triantafillidou & Tsiaras, 2018; Van et al., 2020; Kahn, 2018; Gault, 2012).

2.3 Impact of Government policy on Sustainable tourism management

Van Meter & Van Horn (1975) have proposed a model for the policy implementation process. There are 6 variables that make the policy successful: 1) policy objectives that is clear and unambiguous, 2) allocating adequate resources, 3) making individuals understanding on policy objectives; 4) organizational potential; 5) economic, social and political conditions, and 6) awareness of policy leaders to implement that requires understanding, agree and seriousness in implementing the policy. The Ministry of Tourism and Sports (2015) has defined the components of policy, consisting of economic, social, political and technological aspects. This is consistent with the concept of Panasiuk & Wszendybył-Skulska (2021) who studied on state influence within policy affecting many aspects and social aspects of economic processes, including the need to accurately identify the problems that occur in these areas and necessity

in determining the appropriate approaches and methods of intervention. State intervention in the tourism economy system is aimed at demand, supply, positioning of the tourism economy in the national economy and the relationship with other constituents of the economic structure. Tourism policy is a sector-by-sector policy. It is an activity with elements that consist of economic, political, social and cultural goals related to tourism development. Obtaining a comprehensive positive effect results from the existence of supply and demand, as well as determination to meet social needs in terms of tourism and setting necessary measures.

For the concept of policy components, Wang & Ap (2013) have developed conceptual framework explaining factors affecting the implementation of tourism policies and showing a framework based on the experience of implementing tourism policies at the local level in China. It exposes that there are factors such as macroeconomics and society, institutional arrangements, relations between organizations and inter-organizational coordination structures and interest groups have influence to the implementation of the tourism policy. The conceptual framework describes the factors that affect further implementation of the tourism policy developed from tourism public administrative studies, tourism policy formulation and implementation of general public policies. This conceptual framework is the basis for understanding tourism policy implementation. The implementation of tourism policies depends on the political, economic and social environments in general. Therefore, different empirical case studies in political and economic systems can strengthen the framework with live illustrations of concepts, elements and relationship to facilitate understanding of the implementation of tourism policy in China. The framework of factors influencing the tourism policy implementation was conceptualized by synthesizing tourism education, public administration, tourism planning and supervision, and auditing destination marketing organizations to identify factors affecting the implementation of tourism policy. The concept of public administration and general policy implementation to create concepts about 4 factors: 1) macro environment such as the economic and social environments, etc. 2) institutional management such as public sector management, values and understanding of tourism management and tourism, etc., 3) relationship between organizations and coordination, and 4) interest groups, especially the socio-economic environment affecting the role governments on tourism development (Van Meter & Van Horn, 1975); Van et al., 2020).

2.4 Impact of Potential of tourist attraction on Sustainable tourism management

Potential tourist attractions will affect tourism in which the tourist attraction potential as conceptualized by Dickman (1996) consists of 5A main components: 1) attraction, 2) accessibility, 3) amenities, 4) accommodation, and 5) activities. Cooper & Boniface (1998) have stated that a tourist attraction is an important place to meet the needs of tourists, consisting of 4As: 1) attractions should have something to attract tourists or looks inviting or have a unique charm, 2) accessibility will make attractiveness for tourist attractions, 3) amenities in tourist attractions should create an impression, delight, and appreciation for sightseeing, and 4) ancillary service in tourist attractions should be provided for tourists, agencies and related business sectors to facilitate and attract tourists to visit tourist attractions. This is in line with the study of Andrianto & Sugiana (2016) which reveal that the basic elements necessary for a

suitable place to be developed as a tourism attraction should consist of 4A's tourism: attractions, accessibility, amenities, and ancillary.

2.5 Sustainable tourism management

The development of sustainable tourism sites has attracted a lot of attention from researchers for many years, particularly concerning the positive and negative impacts of tourism on tourism resources and communities (Mihalič et al., 2016). This is consistent with Amerta, Sara & Bagiada (2018), stating that the tourism sector plays an important role in the development of the world economy over the past three decades. The sector provides basic income support to many countries around the world. The development of tourism in today's world is relevant in the field of cultural heritage conservation and sustainable conservation of the natural environment. Many tourist attractions began to reduce their socio-cultural and environmental impacts from tourism. The current tourism development tends to no longer adapt to the development of mass tourism. However, it is in the form of tourism development that is of particular interest or is considered an alternative tourism development (Mihalic, 2016).

For sustainable tourism development, the world's leading quality tourist attractions that grow has equilibrium based on Thai identity to promote socio-economic development and distribute income to people in all sectors sustainably by laying out 5 strategies: 1) developing the quality of tourist attractions, products and services in tourism to create balance and sustainability, 2) developing of infrastructure and facilities to support the expansion of the tourism industry, 3) developing human resource in tourism and supporting people's participation in tourism development, 4) balancing Thai tourism through niche marketing, promoting the Thai Way and building confidence of tourists, and 5) integrating tourism management and promoting international cooperation. An important element or principle of the planned tourism development is based on sustainable development. It includes promoting sustainability of natural resources and the environment by preserving and restoring tourist attractions at risk of deterioration, managing capacity to accommodate tourists and cultivating environmentally friendly consciousness, promoting the sustainability of culture by glorifying and preserving Thailand unique, indigenous values and local wisdom (Mihalič et al., 2016; Mihalic, 2016; Amerta, Sara & Bagiada, 2018).

3. METHODOLOGY

The quantitative research approach was used to obtain the findings responding to the research objectives. The study started by collecting the secondary data from textbooks, academic papers, academic articles, research work of doctoral students of universities both in the country and abroad related to management for competitiveness of business entrepreneurs to be used to scrutinize ideas, theories and knowledge until the components of the factors: innovation, tourist attraction potential, government policy and leadership influencing sustainable tourism management in the eastern seaboard tourism development zone. This quantitative research confirms the findings obtained from the population study and from literature review by focusing on presenting academic research results of The Antecedents Affecting Sustainable Tourism Management in the Eastern seaboard Tourism Development Zone.

The quantitative research instrument was a questionnaire. It consists of measures of main variables according to the research conceptual framework. Such measures were developed and adjusted from research in the literature review to match the context of antecedents affecting sustainable tourism management in the eastern seaboard tourism development zone. The data was synthesized and summarized into definition of terms. The indicators of variables according to the research concept were determined. The questionnaire was then constructed according to the 5-level Likert's scale (Likert, 1932), with tryout as well as the validity and reliability tests before collecting data and then statistically analyzing data by using structural equation modeling (SEM). For qualitative research, the researchers concocted in-depth interviews from executives and exports in tourism management in the eastern seaboard tourism development zone. The qualitative data was compiled, categorized, analyzed, interpreted and linked to draw conclusions on the results of the quantitative analysis with more depth, detailed and accurate explanation to confirm and analyze in-depth information.

4. RESULTS

This study used the analysis of exploratory data to test the relationship between the variables by examining the normal distributions of the 15 observed variables studied in the structural equation model, using the chi-square test (χ^2). If it was found to be statistically significant at the .05 level, it means that such variables were non-normally distributed. On the other hand, if it was found to be not statistically significant (P-value > .50), it means that such variables were normally distributed.

Table 1: Statistical test of empirical variables (n=360)

Variables	\bar{x}	S.D.	%CV	sk	Ku	χ^2	P-value
ATTNS	4.08	0.77	18.93	-2.312	-2.918	13.856	.001
ACBLT	4.05	0.79	19.66	-2.209	-3.224	15.272	.000
FCLT	4.06	0.75	18.53	-1.932	-2.538	1.177	.006
CRTVT	4.02	0.79	19.77	-1.940	-4.033	2.031	.000
VISN	4.03	0.78	19.43	-1.994	-3.356	15.240	.000
SCRPB	4.16	0.76	18.30	-2.044	-3.327	15.246	.000
ECPOL	4.12	0.76	18.53	-2.003	-3.330	15.101	.001
SOCPL	3.96	0.80	20.17	-1.545	-3.180	12.499	.002
PLTPL	4.02	0.78	19.40	-1.735	-3.465	15.014	.001
TECPL	4.08	0.74	18.13	-1.865	-3.306	14.406	.001
PRDIN	4.01	0.78	19.59	-1.981	-3.417	15.601	.000
SRVIN	4.20	0.73	17.35	-2.571	-6.109	43.927	.000
MAKIN	3.88	0.85	21.96	-1.669	-2.846	1.883	.004
ORGIN	3.81	0.82	21.73	-1.542	-2.150	7.001	.030
SUSMN	4.15	0.79	19.20	-2.060	-4.168	21.613	.000
ECTRA	3.92	0.82	21.08	-1.565	-3.750	16.514	.000
SOCUL	3.86	0.82	21.35	-1.941	-2.882	12.069	.002
ENVIR	3.93	0.81	20.61	-1.545	-3.433	14.174	.001

Note: chi-square (χ^2) with statistical significance (P-value <.05) indicates a non-normal distribution.

The result of normal score examination by chi-square (χ^2) of empirical variables studied in the structural equation model found that most of the empirical variables in the model had statistical significance ($p < .05$), indicating that most of the empirical variables in the model had a non-normal distribution. Such results may cause the problem in an empirical model fit assessment by of the chi-square test (χ^2). The researchers therefore solved by finding the relative chi-square (χ^2 /degree of freedom). If the value was less than 2.00, it indicated that the model was empirically fit, although the model χ^2 test was statistically significant (p -value $< .05$) (Hair, et al., 2006; Hair et al., 2011).

Table 2: Factor Loadings (n = 360)

Variables	factor loading (λ)	error (θ)	t	R ²
1. Potential of tourist attraction (PTTRA)				
1.1 Attractiveness (ATTNS)	.83	.31	17.77	.69
1.2 Accessibility (ACBLT)	.84	.30	17.98	.70
1.3 Facilities (FCLT)	.78	.39	16.41	.61
$\rho_c = .86 \quad \rho_v = .67$				
2. Leadership (LEADE)				
2.1 Creativity (CRTVT)	.81	.34	16.70	.66
2.2 Vision (VISN)	.77	.41	15.58	.59
2.3 Social responsibility (SCRPB)	.79	.37	16.20	.63
$\rho_c = .83 \quad \rho_v = .63$				
3. Government policy (GOVPL)				
3.1 Economic policy (ECPOL)	.79	.38	16.82	.62
3.2 Social policy (SOCPL)	.82	.33	17.94	.67
3.3 Political policy (PLTPL)	.80	.37	17.18	.63
3.4 Technological policy (TECPL)	.77	.41	16.37	.59
$\rho_c = .87 \quad \rho_v = .63$				
4. Innovation (INOVA)				
4.1 Product innovation (PRDIN)	.77	.41	15.45	.59
4.2 Service innovation (SRVIN)	.79	.37	15.95	.63
4.3 Marketing innovation (MAKIN)	.73	.47	14.28	.53
4.4 Organizational innovation (ORGIN)	.68	.54	12.95	.46
$\rho_c = .83 \quad \rho_v = .55$				
5. Sustainable tourism management (SBTRM)				
5.1 Sustainable management (SUSMN)	.81	.34	17.26	.66
5.2 Economy and trade (ECTRA)	.79	.38	16.64	.62
5.3 Society and culture (SOCUL)	.77	.41	15.67	.59
5.4 Environment (ENVIR)	.79	.38	16.30	.62
$\rho_c = .87 \quad \rho_v = .62$				
chi-square = 0.49, df = 1, P-value = 0.48400, RMSEA = 0.000				

Table 3: Measurement Model (n=360)

Dependent variables	R ²	Effects	Independent variables			
			Innovation (INOVA)	Potential of tourist attraction (PTTRA)	Leadership (LEADE)	Government policy (GOVPL)
Innovation (INOVA)	.94	DE	-	.51*(4.06)	.56*(5.78)	.83*(4.11)
		IE	-	-	-	-
		TE	-	.51*(4.06)	.56*(5.78)	.83*(4.11)
Sustainable tourism management (SBTRM)	.94	DE	.43*(4.30)	.40*(4.26)	.48*(4.90)	.55*(4.62)
		IE	-	.31*(4.06)	.33*(4.82)	.38*(4.71)
		TE	.43*(4.30)	.71*(4.97)	.81*(4.11)	.93*(4.17)

$\chi^2 = 213.17$, $df = 120$, $P\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2/df = 1.77$, $RMSEA = .047$, $RMR = .016$, $SRMR = .025$, $CFI = 1.00$, $GFI = .94$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 276.83$

* Statistically significant at the .05 level

Note: In parentheses, they were the t-value. If the value was not between -1.96 and 1.96, it was statistically significant at the .05 level.

Chi-Square=213.17, df=120, P-value=0.00000, RMSEA=0.047

Figure 1: Adjusted Model (n=360)

The results of the analysis showed that the adjust relationship equation model of the factors influencing sustainable tourism management in the eastern seaboard tourism development zone was fit to the empirical data at an acceptable level which was considered from fit indices as follows: $\chi^2 = 213.17$, $df = 120$, $P\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2/df = 1.77$, $RMSEA = .047$, $RMR = .016$, $SRMR = .025$, $CFI = 1.00$, $GFI = .94$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 276.83$. The estimation was found in the structural equation model as follows:

1. Innovation (INOVA) had a direct effect on sustainable tourism management (SBTRM), with the effect coefficient of .43 and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, the hypothesis 1, innovation has a positive direct effect on sustainable tourism management, was accepted.
2. Potential of tourist attraction (PTTRA) had a direct effect on innovation (INOVA), with the effect coefficient of .51 and statistical significance at the level .05. As a result, hypothesis 2, potential of tourist attraction has a positive direct effect on innovation, was accepted.
3. Potential of tourist attraction (PTTRA) had a direct effect on sustainable tourism management (SBTRM), with the effect coefficient of .40 and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 3, potential of tourist attraction has a direct positive effect on sustainable tourism management, was accepted.
4. Government policy (GOVPL) had a direct effect on innovation (INOVA), with the effect coefficient of .83 and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 4, government policy has a positive direct effect on innovation, was accepted.
5. Government policy (GOVPL) had a direct effect on sustainable tourism management (SBTRM), with the effect coefficient of .55 and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 5, government policy has a positive direct effect on sustainable tourism management, was accepted.
6. Leadership (LEADE) had a direct effect on innovation (INOVA), with the effect coefficient of .56 and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 6, leadership has a direct positive effect on innovation, was accepted.
7. Leadership (LEADE) had a direct effect on sustainable tourism management (SBTRM), with the effect coefficient of .48 and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 7, leadership has a direct positive effect on sustainable tourism management, was accepted.
8. Potential of tourist attraction (PTTRA), leadership (LEADE) and government policy (GOVPL) could jointly predict innovation (INOVA) by 94%.
9. Innovation (INOVA), potential of tourist attraction (PTTRA), leadership (LEADE) and government policy (GOVPL) could jointly predict sustainable tourism management (SBTRM) by 94%.

5. CONCLUSION

Results of general information of the 360 sample tourism entrepreneurs in an accommodation business, food and beverage business, tour business, transport business, merchandise and souvenir business, and service business from tourist attractions in the eastern seaboard tourism development zone, including Chonburi, Rayong, Chanthaburi and Trat was found that most of the samples were in food and beverage business group, 94 people, representing 26.00 percent. They were 193 females, representing 53.50 percent, 119 41-to-55-year-old people, representing 33.00 percent, 162 managers, representing 45.00 percent, 236 people graduated not higher than a bachelor's degree, representing 65.50 percent, and 148 people with working period of 6-15 years, representing 41.00 percent. The results found that the potential of tourist attraction, leadership, government policy, innovation and sustainable tourism management in the eastern seaboard tourism development zone are at a high level.

Path relationship equations between causal variables (Independent variables) that has a direct effect on the dependent variables in the adjust model shows that tourism potential, leadership and government policy have a direct effect on innovation, with the effect coefficients of .51, .56 and .83, respectively, statistical significance at the .05 level, and the variance explanation of 94%. Moreover, innovation, potential of tourist attraction, leadership and government policy have a direct effect on sustainable tourism management (SBTRM), with the effect coefficients of .43, .40, .48 and .55, respectively, statistical significance at the .05 level, and the variance explanation of 94%. Relationship path equation between the exogenous variables that have a total effect on the endogenous variables (Reduced equations) that were studied in the adjust model showed that exogenous variables, comprising potential of tourist attractions, leadership, and government policy, have a total effect on innovation, with the effect coefficients of .51, .56 and .83, respectively, statistical significance at the .05 level, and prediction ability of 94%. In addition, exogenous variables, consisting of potential of tourist attraction, leadership, and government policy, have a total effect on sustainable tourism management, with the effect coefficients of .71, .81 and .93, respectively, statistical significance at the .05 level, and prediction ability of 83%.

After obtaining findings from the study, the researchers have created the sustainable tourism management model in the eastern seaboard tourism development zone: GLTI-STM model (G = Government Policy, L = Leadership, T = Tourist Attraction Potential, I = Innovation, STM = Sustainable Tourism Management).

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